

success story

Pilot 2: Sustainable Agriculture National scale

Horizon 2020 EIFFEL project | developing tools for monitoring climate change indicators

The National Paying Agency (NPA) participates in the EIFFEL project, which is an international research and innovation project funded by the European Union (EU) Horizon 2020 programme. The goal of the project – development of tools for monitoring climate change indicators thus contributing to the mitigation of climate change. The EU Horizon 2020 project EIFFEL "Global Earth Observation System (GEOSS) Applications for Climate Change" aims to develop tools for monitoring climate change adaptation indicators, exploit the potential of existing untapped GEOSS data sets, encourage the use of artificial intelligence tools in the process of developing climate change impact indicators, to promote the joint development of climate change adaptation and mitigation programmes, to create a common set of these programmes to be used in different areas. The project involves 19 participants from 8 European countries and aims to create tools for transport management, water and land use management, sustainable agriculture, sustainable urban development, resilience to natural disasters. NPA, within the project being responsible for the sustainable agriculture, in collaboration with partners from the National Athens Observatory' Earth Observation Center "Beyond" and the Balkan Environment Centre, is developing a set of tools for sustainable agriculture.

On 22 November 2022, a meeting of project participants developing climate change monitoring tools for sustainable agriculture took place in the headquarters of the NPA in Vilnius, Lithuania. During the event pilot products developed for sustainable agriculture services to monitor and evaluate soil properties influencing greenhouse gas emissions, were demonstrated. Representatives of the Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, the Lithuanian Centre for Agricultural and Forestry Sciences, the Environmental Protection Agency, the Ministry of the Environment and the Ministry of Agriculture also participated in the meeting. The developed tools will be available to national paying agencies, farmers, policy makers and other stakeholders.

It is expected that the developed tools for monitoring climate change indicators will speed up the transition to climate-resilient agricultural activities and mitigate more effectively the effects of climate change. The results of the project will be used by NPA for more transparent, effective and goal-oriented Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) implementation, also by farmers and policy makers to manage local and national microclimate effects more efficiently in support of a shift towards a low carbon and climate resilient economy in the agriculture. The ongoing project will also extensively contribute to the successful implementation of the Area Monitoring System by making efficient use of digital solutions and e-tools, by creating reliable methodologies and harmonised data sets for monitoring agricultural performance while reducing administrative burden for farmers, PA's and other stakeholders.

Thus the implementation of the project contributes not only to developing innovative tools but also brings together national institutions who collaborate in achieving the same goal – mitigation of climate change effects.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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 eiffel4climate project

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